

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B413
 Date: 03 Nov 2008
 Take Off: 11:03:35
 Landing: 16:05:47
 Flight Time 5h02m12s

Campaign: VOCALS – Ilo Pollution Gradient Study

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the west coast of northern Chile & southern Peru

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Jackie Mullholland	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Grant Allen	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Steve Abel	Manchester University	
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
7	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
9	SWS/SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
12	MARSS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
13	AMS/SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
14	Wet neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
15	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
16	Manchester cloud	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
17	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
18	Familiarisation	Guy Gratton	Brunel	
19				

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B413
 Date: 03/11/08
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Arica, Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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104446		Start-Up	0.03 kft	025	engine start
105015		!	0.03 kft	025	start taxi
110335		T/O	0.00 kft	214	
110335	110946	Profile 1	0.00 - 6.0 kft	231	
110856		!	5.2 kft	290	JW/Nevzorov zero
110947	111209	Run 1	6.0 - 5.9 kft	294	
111214	111517	Profile 2	5.8 - 2.9 kft	293	
111531		ASP	2.9 kft	297	open (late!)
111517	112654	Run 2	2.9 - 3.0 kft	296	
111920		!	3.0 kft	295	JW/Nevzorov zero
112138		!	2.9 kft	297	Heimann shutter opened
112151		!	2.9 kft	296	BBR shutter retract
112258		!	2.9 kft	298	Heimann cal
112702	112841	Profile 3	3.0 - 4.8 kft	294	
112846	113043	Run 4	4.9 kft	301	
113052	113653	Profile 4	4.9 - 0.05 kft	292	
113517		!	0.84 kft	298	change to 500 fpm
113654	114205	Profile 5	0.05 - 5.0 kft	293	
114205	114827	Profile 6	5.0 - 0.05 kft	297	
114312		!	3.8 kft	295	JW zero
114658		!	0.67 kft	294	change to 500 fpm
114827	115451	Profile 7	0.05 - 6.0 kft	296	
115007		!	1.4 kft	296	JW/Nevzorov zero
115915	120654	Profile 8	5.9 - 0.05 kft	111	
120150		!	3.7 kft	113	JW zero
120655	121313	Profile 9	0.05 - 6.0 kft	117	
121313	122057	Profile 10	6.0 - 0.05 kft	119	
122057	122703	Profile 11	0.05 - 5.0 kft	115	
122703	123453	Profile 12	5.0 - 0.05 kft	119	start 122703
123029		!	3.0 kft	115	JW zero
123509	123828	Profile 13	0.05 - 3.2 kft	120	
123837	124114	Run 5	3.3 kft	116	
123950		!	3.3 kft	117	JW/Nevzorov zero
124411	124757	Run 6	2.3 kft	292	& JW/Nevzorov zero
124554		!	2.4 kft	301	Heimann cal
124806	124827	Profile 14	2.3 - 2.0 kft	296	
124834	125136	Run 7	2.0 - 2.1 kft	297	
125144	125205	Profile 15	2.1 - 2.2 kft	293	

125206	132159	Run 8	2.2 kft	294	
132200	132257	Profile 16	2.2 - 2.9 kft	302	
132314	132340	Profile 16	2.8 - 3.3 kft	329	
132601	133606	Run 9	3.3 kft	121	
133613	133720	Profile 17	3.3 - 4.3 kft	118	
133726	133923	Run 10	4.3 kft	114	
133946	134024	Run 11	4.5 kft	118	
134024	134130	Profile 18	5.2 - 5.4 kft	116	
134137	134434	Run 12	5.4 kft	112	
134440	134459	Profile 19	5.5 - 5.7 kft	114	
134508	134639	Run 13	5.8 kft	114	
134645	134924	Profile 20	5.8 - 3.3 kft	113	
134938	134952	Run 14	3.3 kft	113	
134959	135019	Profile 21	3.3 - 3.1 kft	113	
135027	135547	Run 15	3.2 - 3.1 kft	114	
135623	135819	Profile 22	3.1 - 1.6 kft	182	
135946	140906	Run 16	1.4 - 1.3 kft	227	
140235		!	1.4 kft	234	Heimann cal
140333		!	1.3 kft	230	JW/Nevzorov zero
140906	141121	Profile 23	1.3 - 0.05 kft	232	
141122	142120	Run 17	0.1 kft	231	
142121	142422	Profile 24	0.05 - 3.0 kft	230	
142429	143423	Run 18	3.1 kft	237	
143430	143507	Profile 25	3.2 - 3.8 kft	240	
143529	144509	Run 19	3.8 - 4.2 kft	239	
143642		!	3.8 kft	237	JW/Nevzorov zero
144517	145017	Profile 26	4.2 - 0.05 kft	238	
144859		!	0.8 kft	233	change to 500 fpm
145036	145239	Profile 27	0.05 - 2.3 kft	240	
145250	145755	Run 20	2.3 kft	237	
145430		!	2.3 kft	235	JW/Nevzorov zero
145807	145944	Profile 28	2.3 - 3.7 kft	233	
145958	150950	Run 21	3.9 - 3.7 kft	065	
150957	152502	Profile 29	3.7 - 23.0 kft	070	
151615		!	10.4 kft	069	JW zero
152822	153938	Run 22	23.0 kft	067	
152822		Sonde 1	23.0 kft	067	
152840		Sonde 2	23.0 kft	067	

153321		Sonde 3	23.0 kft	073
153513		!	23.1 kft	068 JW/Nevzorov zero
153932		Sonde 4	23.0 kft	069
153946	160205	Profile 30	23.0 - 2.0 kft	069
155335		!	9.5 kft	072 JW/Nevzorov zero
160013		!	3.9 kft	027 Heimann close.
160013		!	3.9 kft	027 BBR shutter extend
160547		Land	0.08 kft	201

B413 Track 03-NOV-08

SCAR -> SCDA - Overview

NavData Cycle 2008-11 Expires: Thursday, 20 November 2008.
Scale: 1:1891527 (1 inch = 25.94 naut mi). Printed on 02 Nov 2008

76996 ; 68

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

FAAM Sortie, Flight B413
Mon 3rd November 2008
VOCALS Flight B413 – ILO Pollution gradient study

T/O **0800 local (1100 UTC)**
Land **1300 local (1600 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Grant Allen, Steve Abel

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile and Peru.

Waypoints:

P1: 73° 30' W 17° S
P2: 71° 9'W, 18° 7' S
P3: 71° 42'W, 17°50' S
P4: 75° W, 20° S

Sortie Objectives: To characterise aerosol and SO₂/Sulphate plumes from the Ilo smelter on the Peruvian coast and to examine the gradient in smelter pollution from Ilo out to the pristine marine environment, studying its impact on marine Sc microphysics if present. The Dornier-228 will collaborate – flight pattern highlighted in pink on Google Earth way-points below.

Weather: High pressure system over the SE Pacific capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore northerly flow from overland Peru, due to an anticyclone to the North, bringing pollution plumes from onshore to the north of Arica and suppressing Sc development on the coast and near shore due to dry subsidence.

Information:

Latest satellite image will be inserted prior to take-off

Flight patterns:

1. Take off from Arica and profile ascent at 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl to check instrumentation

[6 min; T=0h 6 min]

2. Continue en route to point P1, beginning saw-tooth cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 50ft.

[54 min; T=1h 00 min]

Cycle consisting of

- a. profile descent to 50ft amsl,
- b. profile ascent to 6000 ft (or just above cloud if present),

3 At point P1 turn to fly reciprocal path along a straight and level in cloud at a level to be determined by the mission scientist to point P2

[45 mins, T= 1h 45 m]

4. Turn onto reciprocal heading to fly straight and level run between P2 and P1 below cloud at a level determined by the mission scientist.

[45m; T=2h 30m]

5. Ascend and fly straight and level above cloud at a level determined by the mission scientist between P1 and P3

[30m, T=3h 0m]

6. At P3, turn and fly en route to P4, performing a series of 10-minute straight and level runs below, within and above cloud at altitude advised by the mission scientist.

[60 m, T=4h 0m]

7. At P4, turn to return en route directly to Arica with profile ascent to FL230, releasing a dropsonde at start of high level run.

[23m, T=4h 23m]

8. Release dropsondes at 5-minute intervals during high level return, until start of profile descent into Arica at 1000 ft/min. Continue profile descent until as late as possible before landing.

[60m, T=5h 10m]

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Dropsondes – 1 every 5-minutes on high level leg between P4 and Arica

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

BAe-146 Flight B413 flight summary
Mon 3rd November 2008
VOCALS Flight B413 – ILO Pollution gradient study

T/O **0800 local (1100 UTC)**
Land **1300 local (1600 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Grant Allen, Steve Abel

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile and Peru.

Waypoints:

P1: 73° 30' W 17 ° S
P2: 71° 9' W, 18° 7' S
P3: 71° 42' W, 17°50' S
P4: 75° W, 20° S

Sortie Objectives: To characterise aerosol and SO₂/Sulphate plumes from the Ilo smelter on the Peruvian coast and to examine the gradient in smelter pollution from Ilo out to the pristine marine environment, studying its impact on marine Sc microphysics if present. The Dornier-228 will collaborate – Dornier flight pattern highlighted in pink on Google Earth way-points below.

Information:

1/ Google Earth flight track (purple line shows Dornier track)

2/ NAME Model SO₂ Forecast 0-1000 magl for 0900 local

NAME III (version 5.2)

Run name: VOCALS support

1hr 0min average Air Concentration

Z = 500.0000 m agl

Valid at 03/11/2008 12:00 UTC

Start of release: -infinity

Pollutant: SO2

3/ GOES Image (0528 local)

Flight pattern:

1. After take-off from Arica, we flew a series of saw-tooth profiles en route to P1 between 50 ft amsl and 6000 ft amsl. No evidence of significant chemical or aerosol pollution plumes were noted below cloud. Cloud base was noted to be ~ 2000 ft and cloud base was initially 2900 ft. On the above-cloud leg of these profiles, two discrete pollution layers were noted at around 3200 ft and 4500 ft, as seen by increased dry nephelometer concentrations and CO up to 87 ppbv with slight increases in ozone to 20 ppbv (although this maybe unrealistically low due to instrument problems). AMS and VACC reported that this aerosol was mostly of sulphate composition. Droplet concentrations on this run were noted to be approximately 400-500 cc-1. Mean droplet diameters were noted to be approximately 15 um.
2. After a turn toward a reciprocal path toward P2, we continued the saw-tooth pattern. On the return leg, cloud LWC reduced along the run, consistent with the decrease and thinning in cloud cover observed from the flight deck. Cloud droplet number and droplet diameter remained broadly similar to those noted on the outbound leg. Some cumulus fractus cloud was noted to be detached and lower than the surrounding Sc deck.
3. We then turned toward a reciprocal path toward P1 at an altitude of 2500 ft to fly a straight and level leg in cloud. Cloud droplet numbers were around 450-500 cc-1 with diameter around 15 um.
4. After a turn on a reciprocal path toward P3, we climbed to 3500 ft to sample the pollution layer above cloud in a 10-minute straight and level run. CN reported values between 1000 – 1500 with CO around 92 ppbv. AMS saw mostly sulphate with some organics (highest sulphate in VOCALS thus far). There was a gradual reducing gradient across this leg.
5. This was followed by an ascent to 4500 ft to sample the higher of the two layers for a 10-minute run. This layer was less distinct than that below.
6. At point 3, we turned to face a radial with point 4 and descended to 100 ft amsl for a 10-minute run. No significant aerosol or chemical structure was noted on the profile below cloud. Some small cumulus was noted to be lower than the surrounding Sc deck. A weak temperature inversion was noted at ~1000 mb on the descending profile – a small increase in moisture was noted in this inversion layer.
7. We then ascended to 3200 ft for an in-cloud run for 10 minutes. Droplet concs were around 250-300 cc-1 and mean volume diameter was again around 17 um. LWC between 0.2-0.35. Cloud base was noted to be around 3000 ft. During this run, we made radio contact with the Dornier, which reported Grimm total concentrations in a polluted layer of 11000 ft in excess of 350 cc-1.
8. We then ascended above cloud for a 10-minute run, initially at 3800 ft, increasing to 4200 ft due to the increasing cloud top height on this SW leg out to sea. Small increases in CO up to 75 ppbv were noted just above cloud. Cloud base was noted at 2600 ft.
9. We then descended to 50 ft amsl, followed by an immediate ascent to 2500 ft for a 10-minute run. Again, no polluted structure was noted on the profile below cloud.
10. After turning on a radial back to Arica at point 4, we climbed to 4000 ft initially for an in-cloud run for 10 mins. Cloud top dropped as we continued en route toward the coast, meaning we had to drop to 3800 ft to stay within cloud.

11. We then performed a profile climb to 23000 ft, noting two discrete weakly polluted layers above cloud at 4500 ft, and between 7000 ft to 11000 ft. CO within this layer was noted to be up to 90 ppbv with AMS reporting all sulphate with some organic.

12. At 23000 ft, 2 sondes were dropped immediately at the end of the climb, followed by 2 more at 5-minute intervals.

13. We then descended toward Arica in a profile descent at 1000 ft/min until end of science at 1700 ft. Layers of weak polluted air were noted above cloud at similar altitudes as those seen previously.

In summary, there was no evidence of polluted airmasses below cloud. Above cloud some small layers of aged polluted air were seen. No strong evidence of a plume from the Ilo smelter was observed.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.413** Date 3/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30		0	'	'	Surface conditions. No wind.
					no cloud, ~18°C, sunny,
					visibility ~ 20km. Pres 1012 mb.
					Instrument status: Only one channel working
11:04					on CCN.
					Take-off - delayed slightly for clearance.
11:04	P1		NW		Profile ascent to 6000 ft.
11:14	P2L		NW		To 3000 ft for CVI cal.
11:16					SLL at 3000 ft for CVI cal.
					Cap at 930 mb - T inversion
					not as strong as normal.
11:30					Ascent to 5000 ft - to clear route
					for AMS.
					CO > 85 ppbv.
11:31	P4				Scoops to 50ft saw tooth.
11:37	P5T		NW		Saw tooth to 500ft
					CVI reports to problem *
11:41	P6L				To 50ft.
					200-2m 17m - ISSP. Cloud physics
					reporting drizzle.
					AMS reporting all sulphate.
11:48	P7T				50ft to 6000ft. Higher to get
					plume above cloud.
11:54:51					87 ppbv CO, O ₃ > 70 ppbv.
					Thin and horizontally varying layer.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.413** Date Name Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:58	P84		NW		6000ft → 50ft
					CCN: 1000 → 40 /cc
					CO ₂ > 90 ppbv, O ₃ = 14 ppbv
12:00					Pollution layer above cloud only
					Cloud base = 2000ft
					Cloud top = 2900ft
					CDP = 150. Dia = 18 at CTH.
					13-16µm mean diameter from 200
12:07	P9↑		P12		to 6000ft
12:13	P10↓				6000ft to 50ft. Thin layers are
12:21	P11↑				between 3000 and 4500ft
					CAS 400, 500 at bottom of cloud.
12:31	P12↓				6000ft to 50ft. 2 layers above
					cloud.
					LWC lower than one before. LWC
					has changed on these 2 profiles.
12:43	R	2500ft			Cloud runs
12:50					Entering cloud.
12:52					CDP: 125 → 250. Dia: 17µm. CDP.
					FSSP: 15µm. 350 → 550 cores.
					LWC: 0.17, 450 → 500 cores.
					12 → 13µm - V. thin cloud.
13:09					12 → 13 - LWC 0.25 → 0.1
					12 → 10/L - Drizzle.
13:22					Climb to 3000ft to look for
					180 aerosol layer.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...413 Date 3/11/08 Name G. Allen Page 3 of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:30:	Ru 13	3500ft			1500 → 1000 - CCN Wet neph increase. CO > 92 ppbv. This layer. AMS / UACC reports 750 counts/CCN.
13:36	P ↑				To 4500 ft.
13:46	P2 ↓				To 3500 ft - To get 1st aerosol layer. Evidence of layer at 4500 ft - very thin CCN reported increase
13:57			P3		Turn to P4 + descent to 500ft below cloud. No structure in aerosol on descent.
14:09	P23 ↓				Descent to 100ft. Some thicker cumulus lower than surrounding SC.
14:22	P24 ↑ P18				Ascent to cloud layer 3200ft in cloud Base at 3000ft. CAS 200 → 800km 0.35 LWC. D _{in} = 17 μm. O ₂ → 0.35 LWC. Cirrus 2/8 / mb. 10° 13' 00" ± 1'
14:30	P19		13 → 14		at ↑ Dornier report ↑
14:	P24 ↑				110 → 1000km - Dornier
14:35:00					Above cloud - slight increase in CO → 75 ppbv

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 413 Date 3/11/08 Name G. ALLEN Page 4. of 5

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14:42		4300ft			Sc cloud base rising ~ 3800ft - and thickening
14:48	P2SB				Descent to 50ft followed by climb to 2500 ft -
					Through cloud 100 → 200. CDP. Cores. FSSP: 300/μm.
14:51					50 → 2500 1.6μm → 1.0μm.
					320 → 420 cloud base. 0.2 → 0.15.
14:58					8000ft climb in cloud.
15:00	R21	4000	14 → 16		Short run in cloud -
					Cloud base ^{top} drop dropping on return to east - Descending to 3800ft to stay in cloud -
15:04		3800ft			1.3 → 1.5 μm with a dip. 300 → 400/μm 0.25 → 0.1 LWC.
15:10	P2BT	23000ft			Layer at 7600 ft. alt. 5000ft - continuously polluted layer on ascent. CO up to 90ppbv - Sulphate - 300 → 800. Top of layer at 11000ft - all dropped down.
15:18					Sc deck appears less convective than usual - less cellular contrast, flatter CTH.
15:28					Dropsonde released x2 in succession at 23000ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B413 Date 3/10/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page ...1... of ...7...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
110443	T/O				Time since ~ 930 - 800 mbar
	P1↑				Structure in Td above inversion. (and within). No cloud at coast though → burst off in morning?
110947	R1	6000'			Check instrumentation
111214	P2↓	6000 - 3000'			Sea & cut to West away from coast.
111517	END				
111634	R2	3000'			Sea level ~ 25m ⁻¹ CO ~ 73ppb O ₃ ~ 11ppb. Sea to West looks lower than 3000' 17.97W drip off in sea to 16N ⁻¹ Above this sea.
112300					
112630					Sea increased to 25m ⁻¹ CO ~ 75ppb O ₃ ~ 10ppb Still above cloud.
112654	R2	END			
	P3↑	3000 - 5000'			CO ↑ to 85ppb O ₃ ↑ 15ppb → Pollution above cloud.
112841	END				Sea ~ 25m ⁻¹
112846	R4	5000'			
113052	P4↓	5000' - 50'			Begin sawtooth leg;
		2700'			Cloud top LWC ~ 0.25gm ⁻³
		2000'			Cloud base MWD ~ 18-19µm
					CO dropped off to 70ppb below cloud Sea ~ 20m ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.413... Date 3/11/08... Name STEVE ABEL... Page 2... of 7...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
113656	P5T	50'			Some small drizzle drops (~100 μ m) 200 μ m below cloud. Cloud top 2700' COP ~ 150cc $^{-1}$ FSP ~ 300-600 LWC ~ 0.3gm $^{-3}$ CO increasing above cloud to 86 ppb O ₃ ~ 28 ppb $^{-1}$
114205	P6b	5000'			Neph suggests some structure in aerosol above cloud varies between 2517 $^{-1}$ and 5m $^{-1}$. More drizzle in this profile through cloud. FSP ~ 17 μ m LWC ~ 0.3gm $^{-3}$. AMS predominantly sulphate - 1-2gm $^{-3}$ small amounts of organocr. CO ↓ off to 68 ppb below cloud.
114827	P7T	50'			Inversion at 970 - 980mbar consistent with stratiform (flocus) cloud below Sc. Decoupled boundary layer. Main Sc layer ~ LWC ~ 0.3gm $^{-3}$ CO increased above cloud to ~ 88 ppb and decreased to 77 ppb O ₃ also shows thin layer of aerosol above Sc.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...413... Date 3.11.08... Name STEVE ABEL... Page 3 of 7...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
115350		6000'			O ₃ and CO increasing again. Pollution variable in horizontal and vertical.
115919	P8↓	6000'			2 layers of pollution above cloud 3700' and 5000' Lower layer extends down to cloud top → entrainment into cloud? Cloud top ~ 2000' LWC patch ~ 0.2g m ⁻³ . Not much drizzle. CAP 150cc ⁻¹ MWD 18µm, FSSP 600cc ⁻¹ MWD 1µm CAS 400cc ⁻¹ MWD ~ 15µm. CO and O ₃ dropping off below cloud.
120655	P9↑	500'			Cloud LWC ~ 0.3g m ⁻³ AMS → sulphate increased when come out of cloud top
121313	P10↓	6000'			Pollution layers above cloud again. LWC ~ 0.2g m ⁻³ CAS 600cc ⁻¹ by cloud 320cc ⁻¹ lower down in cloud. CO dropped off below cloud to 7ppb CCN → layer 2000' and at bottom of profile. Neph O ₃ also higher below cloud than on previous runs → Nearer 110 smelter.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.4.13. Date 3/11/07... Name STEVE ABEL... Page 4 of 7...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
122057	P11↑	50'			COP - 200 cc ⁻¹
					FSSP - 450-500 cc ⁻¹
					LWC 0.3 gm ⁻³
					CAS 450 cc ⁻¹ MVD 15 μm ⁿ
					Possibly higher than further North because more 110?
	P12↓				Again CO dropped off below cloud. LWC ~ 0.1 gm ⁻³
					Cloud thinning !!
123453	P13↑	50'			Run 11: LUSATC satellite image show cloud cleared away from coast on SE end of leg. More cloud @ NW end.
124411	R6	2500'			CO 73 ppb O ₃ 13 ppb O ₅ 16 μm ⁻¹
124700					Very thin cloud below us. Going to descend to try and get S ahead of us.
124834	R7	2300'			Cloud run. Cloud thin at SE leg of run. LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³ Very near cloud base can see sea surface.
125256	R8	2600'			Nearer cloud top LWC ~ 0.1 gm ⁻³ COP 125-250 cc ⁻¹ MVD - 17 μm FSSP 300-500 cc ⁻¹ MVD - 15 μm CAS 450-500 cc ⁻¹ MVD - 12-13 μm LWC 0.15 gm ⁻³

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.413. Date 3/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 5 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
125530					Cloud very patchy. Evidence of coarse mode and even accumulation mode aerosol on CAS.
125600					w peaks of $2 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. LWC 0.2g m^{-3} ZOC - variable drizzle along run but 10-100 μm^{-1} but all fairly small droplets 100-200 μm .
131500					Increase in drizzle. LWC $\sim 0.3 \text{g m}^{-3}$
132000					Cloud becoming patchy at end of run.
132601	R9	3300'			Run above cloud top in pollution layer. $\sigma_{\text{sea}} \sim 40 \text{m}^{-1}$ CO $\sim 90 \text{ppb}$. PCASP $\sim 5000 \text{cc}^{-1}$! Still incredible high concs. CN 1500 $\rightarrow$ 1000 cc^{-1} as fly to south. Consistent with neph. CO $\sim 93 \text{ppb}$ AMS mainly sulphate with some organics. VA CC highest sulphate concs observed in VOAcs so far.
133330					CN dropped off to 750cc^{-1} CO still at 92ppb $\sigma_{\text{sea}} \sim 20 \text{m}^{-1}$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...413... Date 3/11/08... Name STEVE ABEC... Page 6 of 7...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R12-R13	5600 - 5800'			Two ^{short} SLRS trying to get pollution layer but relatively low aerosol conc. $\sigma_{sc} 10-20 m^{-3}$ Fairly thin layer.
135027	R15	3200'			$\sigma_{sc} \sim 20 m^{-3}$ CO - 86 ppb
135547	R15	END			End at P3 turn to head outboard from coast.
135623	P22 $\downarrow$	3200' - 1500'			Cloud very thin LWC $\sim 0.1 gm^{-3}$
	P23 $\downarrow$	3800' - 1500'			Pass through small inversion $\sim 1000 mbar$. Also Td $\uparrow$ in this layer.
141122	R17	100' run.			σ_{sc} fairly constant $\sim 12 m^{-3}$ See small Cu stragglers where we picked up lower inversion in P23.
142120	P24 $\uparrow$	100'			Cloud base 2800'
142429	R18				CAS 280-300 cc $^{-1}$ MWD 17 μm ESSP consistent with CAU CDP 100 cc $^{-1}$ MWD 29 μm Do ^{not} measure aerosol layers from 13000 - 11000'
143430	P25 $\uparrow$				Cloud top $\sim 3400'$
143529	R19	3800'			Above cloud run CO - 75 ppb Neph $\sigma_{sc} \sim 0!$
144112					Cloud top rising slightly as go to work.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.413 Date 3/11/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 7 of 7

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
144509	P26↓				Cloud top 4200'
					Cloud base 2600'
					CAJ-100-200cc ⁻¹ MVD 17µm cloud top
					FSP-300-400cc ⁻¹ MVD 18µm
					Again small inversion just below 1000mbar
					CAJ 300-400cc ⁻¹ MVD 16µm cloud top
145036	P27↑	100'			
145250	R20	2300'			5cc ~ 10M ⁻¹ red green blue neph
145807	P28↑	2300'			on top of each other. Very different to when sampling aerosol earlier in flight when had good separation of red, green and blue in legs above & near to coast.
145958	R21	3800'			In cloud.
					CAJ ~ 300cc ⁻¹ MVD ~ 15µm
150910	P29	3800 → FL230			Couple of moist layers in profile
					Small aerosol layer ~ 3-3.5km.
					Possibly what R228 sampled but very low concentrations.
152822	R22				High level run dropping sensor.
153946	P30↓	FL230			Moist layer 500-600mbar.
					Lots of T inversions in profile.

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/11/03 19:13

Author of report: Grant Allen

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/11/03 19:20

Remaining flight hours: 35

General Comments:

After mission on Ilo pollution flight on 3/11/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	7 sondes launched - 2 had no wind data.

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	lower SHIMS working today
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	Ozone readings vert low (12-25 ppbv range in-flight), could be realistic, needs comparison
17.	NOx	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO2 (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	not carried in VOCALS
21.	CH4/CO2 (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH4/N2O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	anomalous high counts observed. Needs investigation.
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	not fitted
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	needs alignment
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	only 1 channel working (0.1 superstauration), 2nd will be working for next flight
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	probable contamination from inlet, water noted
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	

42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment: zero calcs were not made, also anonolously low values reported in cloud
43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:
44.	CAPS	Comment:
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment: removed for this flight
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment: not fitted
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:
51.	SATCOM H	Comment: Xchat working well. Phone not available.
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 03 Nov 2008

Flight: B413

Operator: Doug Anderson / Guy Gratton

Page 1 of 2

Preflight

No.	? or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Gases</u>				
1	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
2	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	176
3	X	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
4	X	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	45
5	X	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
6	X	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	31
<u>Flows</u>				
7	X	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 07. LPM on both channels	
8	X	NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	X	NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	X	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	X	CO pressure cell	~ 7.5 bar	
12	X	CO pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	CO time synch @ 08:56:09
<u>Zeros</u>				
13	X	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	X	NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	X	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	09:18:00 to 09:39:21
16	X	SO ₂ zero (not for most flights)	Left for approx 10 min	
<u>Other</u>				
17	X	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
18	X	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
19	No	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
20	n/a	230V	230V power breakers on	
21	n/a	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
22	n/a	Laptop	On and software working	
23	n/a	Data	Being saved to correct directories	
Post flight				
<u>Switch Off</u>				
1	X	CO	Switch off instrument	
2	X	Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	X	NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	X	Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	X	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
<u>Gases (note pressures)</u>				
6	X	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	
7	X	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	
8	X	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	
<u>Driers</u>				
9	X	Small drier	Change if spent	
10	X	Large drier	Change if spent	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
11	n/a	Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	n/a	Laptop	Shut down	
13	n/a	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
<u>Log</u>				
14	X	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	None	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	n/a	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

Date: 03 Nov 2008

Flight: B413

Operator: Doug Anderson / Guy Gratton

Page 2 of 2

In flight

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.
During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
10:37:33	Ground, pre power c/o	92.64	311.49	28856.97	39.67	7.51
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
10:45:56	Ground, pre power c/o	91.58	315.23	28868.27	40.36	7.51
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
10:53:16	Ground, during taxi	91.78	311.50	28588.43	40.21	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

Flight level	Zero Start time	Zero End time	Counts (Hz)	Span Start time	Span End time	Conc. Range	Counts range	Pressure Cell (Torr)	Lamp Temp	O3 Intensities
6000'	11:13:05	11:13:50	28157 - 28518	11:13:55	11:14:46	508-516	75749 - 76263	7.52	40.48	123032
3000'	11:21:30	11:22:12	28231 - 28834	11:22:26	11:23:15	506 - 522	75205 - 76515	7.54	40.52	119727
3500'	12:38:30	12:39:15	28155 - 28690	12:39:17	12:40:05	518 - 532	75342 - 77096	7.53	39.09	114989
3300'	12:26:34	12:27:15	28100 - 29052	12:27:18	12:28:17	517 - 529	76092 - 77225	7.51	38.59	113442
1300'	14:01:20	14:02:00	27938 - 28542	14:02:04	14:02:59	522 - 538	76700 - 77300	7.50	38.65	113806
2500'	14:54:50	14:30:55:45	27952 - 28296	14:56:00	14:56:50	519 - 530	76078 - 77353	7.51	38.44	113006
23,000 *	15:30:00	15:30:40	27939-28362	15:31:20	15:32:00	516-530	75800-76500	7.38	39.08	112,810
4,000 **	16:00:00	16:00:40	27976-28605	16:01:00	16:01:40	513-532	75800-77400	7.50	39.71	111,940
* New operator GBG			** Descending into landing							

Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)
Time	Flight level	CO Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	CO Bkgrd (ppbV)	CO Bkgrd Count (Hz)	CO Cell Pressure (Torr)	CO Lamp Temp (deg C)

In flight comments

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 413

Date: 3/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:06:25	2900	0.08	0													FL030	
11:07:34	2700	0.07														FL040	
11:08:35	2700	0.07														FL050	
11:09:45	1400	0.07														End of Profile 1 @ FL060	
11:12:14																Start Profile 2 from FL060	
11:13:06	800	0.06	1													FL050	
11:14:02	2000	0.07														FL040	
11:15:15	3000	0.07														End of Profile 2 & Start Run 1 @ 3000'	
11:16:00	2800	0.07															
11:18:00	2700	0.07															
11:20:00	1400	0.07															
11:22:00	2200	0.07															
11:24:00	2600	0.07															
11:26:00	2200	0.07															
11:27:00																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 3	
11:28:05	3100	0.07														FL040	
11:28:44																End of Profile 3 & Start Run 4	
11:29:00	2800	0.07															
11:31:50																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 4	
11:31:41	2300	0.07														FL040	
11:32:54	2500	0.07														FL030	
11:34:01	1900	0.08	80													FL020	
11:36:58	3800	0.08	81													End of Profile 4 & Start Profile 5 @ 50'	
11:38:10	3100	0.07														FL010	
11:39:14	2500	0.09	94			30	125	400	12			0.6	150	20	0.4	12	FL020
11:41:22	3500	0.09	131														FL040
11:42:07																	End of Profile 5 & Start Profile 6 @ 5000'
11:42:54	3000	0.07															FL040
11:44:06	3000	0.07	138														FL030
11:45:10	2300	0.07	200			150	250	200	10			0.4	120	20	0.3	1	FL020
11:48:27	2500	0.07															End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 @ 50'
11:49:50	2000	0.07															FL010
11:50:50	2000	0.09	210			2	200	300	20			0.5	150	15	0.3	1	FL020
11:52:45	2700	0.07	290														FL040
11:53:54	445	0.07															FL050
11:55:01	500	0.09															End of Profile 7 @ FL060
11:59:15	1400	0.07															Start Profile 8 @ FL060
12:00:11	390	0.07															FL050
12:01:23	2000	0.07															FL040
12:02:45	3500	0.07															FL030
12:03:45	1500	0.07															FL020
12:05:03	2200	0.07															FL010
12:06:53	2800	0.07															End of Profile 8 & Start Profile 9 @ 50'

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.0V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 413

Date: 3/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:08:12	2700	0.07	334													FL010	
12:09:14	2900	0.12	351			170	175	350	15			0.4	150	24	0.3	1	FL020
12:10:50	4000	0.07	400														FL030
12:11:35	300	0.07															FL040
12:12:30	500	0.07															FL050
12:13:14	2200	0.07															End of Profile 9 & Start Profile 10 @ 6000'
12:14:03	1000	0.07															FL050
12:15:18	3000	0.07															FL040
12:16:18	3500	0.07	401														FL030
12:17:30	1800	0.09	459			1		400	13			0.4	150	18	0.15		FL020
12:20:55	4000	0.07															End of Profile @ 50'
12:22:20	2500	0.07	460														FL010
12:23:15	2600	0.08	466			8	100	450	15			0.5	200	20	0.4	12	FL020
12:25:22	3000	0.07	515														FL040
12:26:29	2400	0.07															FL050
12:27:13	2000	0.07															End of Profile 11 & Start Profile 12 @FL060
12:28:12	2100	0.07															FL050
12:29:21	3400	0.07															FL040
12:30:22	2700	0.07															FL030
12:31:40	2200	0.09	557					500	15			0.4	170	15	0.1		FL020
12:34:43	3100	0.07	559														End of Profile 12 & Start Profile 13
12:35:56	3400	0.07															FL010
12:37:08	2500	0.07															FL020
12:38:50																	End of Profile 13 & Start Run 5 @ 3500'
12:39:00	2400	0.07															
12:41:04																	End of Run 5
12:44:02																	Start Run 6 @ 2500'
12:45:00	2500	0.07															
12:47:00	2400	0.07	560														
12:47:59																	End of Run 6 & Start Profile 14
12:48:30																	End of Profile 14 & Start Run 7 @ FL020
12:49:00	2600	0.07															
12:51:00	1300	0.09	634			1											
12:51:41																	End of Run 7
12:52:46																	Start Run 8 @ FL021
12:53:00	1400	0.16	927			18	100	400	12			0.15	150	14	0.2	12	
12:56:00	1400	0.13	1107			2	100	500	15			0.25	250	14	0.2	12	
12:58:00	1800	0.16	1305			2	75	500	12			0.3	250	15	0.3	12	
13:00:00	1200	0.14	1495			10	50	400	12			0.3	200	15	0.2	12	
13:02:00	1700	0.15	1660			10	100	400	10			0.2	200	15	0.2	12	
13:04:00	1900	0.16	1836			25	150	300	12			0.25	180	14	0.3	12	
13:06:00	1500	0.17	2045			30	150	330	13			0.2	200	14	0.2	12	
13:10:00	1200	0.12	2319			30	225	300	14			0.5	150	14	0.4	1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.0V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 413

Date: 3/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:12:00	1200	0.17	2555			35	125	350	12			0.3	150	14	0.1	12	
13:14:00	1300	0.11	2636			15	125	300	12			0.15	200	14	0.2	12	
13:16:00	2500	0.19	2796			45	150	200	15			0.3	150	15	0.4	1	
13:18:00	300	0.17	2896			60	150	200	15			0.35	150	20	0.35	1	
13:20:00	1100	0.09	3013			1		50	15			0.05	100	10	0.05		
13:22:01																	End of Run 8 & Start Profile 16
13:23:40																	End of Profile 16
13:26:05																	Start Run 9 @ 3500'
13:27:00	5000	0.07	3115														
13:29:00	4200	0.07															
13:31:00	3500	0.07															
13:33:00	3000	0.07	3116														
13:35:00	3200	0.07															
13:36:06																	End of Run 9 & Start Profile 17
13:37:13																	End of Profile 17 @ 4500'
13:38:00	600																
13:39:26																	End of Run 10 & Start Profile 18
13:39:48																	End of Profile 18 & Start Run 11
13:40:34																	End of Run 11 & Start Profile 19
13:41:37																	End of Profile 19 & Start Run 12
13:42:00	2000	0.07	3115														
13:44:00	1400	0.07	3116														
13:44:50																	End of Run 12 & Start Profile 20
13:45:03																	End of Profile 20 & Start Run 13 @ 6000'
13:46:00	1400	0.07															
13:46:43																	End of Run 13 & Start P20
13:49:25																	End of P20 & Start Run 14
13:49:56																	End of Run 14 & Start P21
13:50:30																	End of P21 & Start Run 15
13:51:00	3100	0.07															
13:53:00	3000	0.07															
13:55:00	2000	0.07															
13:55:46																	End of Run 15
13:56:33																	Start Profile 22
13:58:19																	End of Profile & Start Run 16 @ 1800'
14:00:00	2500	0.07															
14:02:00	2800	0.07	3139														
14:04:00	2700	0.07															
14:06:00	2800	0.07															
14:08:58																	End of Run 16 & Start Profile 23
14:11:16																	End of Profile 23 & Start Run 17 @ 100'
14:12:00	3000	0.07	3140														
14:14:00	2200	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.0V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 413

Date: 3/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
14:16:00	2700	0.07															
14:18:00	1700	0.07															
14:20:00	1700	0.07															
14:21:20																End of Run 17 & Start P24	
14:22:33	1300	0.07														FL010	
14:23:30	1000	0.07														FL020	
14:24:22																End of Profile 24 & Start Run 18 @ 3200'	
14:25:00	500	0.21	3230			1	100	250	15			0.2	100	17	0.25	12	
14:27:00	900	0.25	3368			40	150	200	16			0.2	100	20	0.3	12	
14:30:00	700	0.24	3517			3	150	300	10			0.1	150	10	0.1	12	
14:32:00	200	0.18	3627			1		200	12			0.12	150	10	0.1	12	
14:34:32																End of Run 18 & Start Profile 19	
14:35:03																End of Profile 25 & Start Run 19	
14:36:00	330	0.08															
14:38:00	260	0.07	3743														
14:40:00	180	0.07															
14:42:00	200	0.07															
14:44:00	180	0.07															
14:45:12																End of Run 19 & Start Profile 26	
14:45:44	500	0.20	3786			2	100	200	15			0.25	150	11	0.1	12	
14:47:27	1300	0.07	3835													FL020	
14:50:40	1300	0.07														End of Profile 26 & Start Profile 27 @ 50'	
14:51:42	1300	0.07														FL010	
14:52:39																End of Profile 27 & Start Run 20 @ 2500'	
14:53:00	1200	0.07	3835			1											
14:55:00	1300	0.07															
14:57:00	1200	0.07															
14:57:55																End of Run 20 & Start Profile 28	
14:59:46																End of Profile 28 & Start Run 21	
15:00:00	1300	0.12	3855			11	100	200	14			0.15	125	15	0.15	12	
15:03:00	800	0.21	4005			20	150	250	13			0.15	125	16	0.2	1	
15:05:00	600	0.18	4098			10	175	200	14			0.05	140	15	0.1	1	
15:07:00	1300	0.18	4259			15	175	200	15			0.27	150	15	0.2	1	
15:09:50																End of Run 21 & Start Profile 29	
15:14:55	470	0.07	4430													FL090	
15:15:54	1000	0.07														FL100	
15:16:48	300	0.07														FL110	
15:18:56	75	0.07														FL130	
15:19:36	100	0.07														FL140	
15:20:35	140	0.07														FL150	
15:21:34	240	0.07														FL160	
15:22:32	110	0.07														FL170	
15:23:53	80	0.07														FL180	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.0V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.6CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.5V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B413	Date	3 Nov 2008	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
15:28:24	1	Launch	409.70 -15.60 6.59 276.80 21.80 0.80 -72.936400 -19.408200 7014.70
15:37:39	1	Splashdown	1016.51 17.28 69.49 175.68 3.20 -11.54 -72.897244 -19.423094 99999.00
15:28:43	2	Launch	411.91 14.05 1.22 0.00 0.00 0.00 -72.908657 -19.398637 99999.00
15:37:46	2	Splashdown	1016.68 17.36 71.46 206.89 4.12 -9.12 -72.871837 -19.412569 99999.00
			Late Launch detect (30 sec into drop)
15:33:24	3	Launch	409.20 -15.70 7.16 277.30 20.10 0.70 -72.459300 -19.259000 7024.10
15:42:52	3	Splashdown	1016.82 17.91 73.84 168.50 3.61 -8.76 -72.422122 -19.273016 99999.00
15:39:24	4	Launch	409.40 -16.50 9.38 291.30 16.00 0.50 -71.900900 -19.080600 7019.80
15:48:31	4	Splashdown	1016.29 18.19 69.91 172.72 3.66 -8.67 -71.872480 -19.092069 99999.00

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B413**

Date 3 Nov 08

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FAAM © 2004

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$	Ph_det levels		Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time: done 094914Z	New filter Tr = 1.000 done	Set to 3.0 lpm: N/A	.0	16	43	Ave =30 s	←Preflight
113256	0.985		5.0	15	42		pump off
113413	.985		11.9	15	42		pump on
113901	.981		.0	15	42		pump off
114046	.982		.0	15	42		pump on
114410	.980		8.3	15	42		pump off
114640	.979		7.1	15	42		pump on
115030	.977		.0	15	42		pump off
115140	.978		.0	15	42		pump on
120240	.973		14.1	15	42		pump off
120402	.972		4.0	15	42		pump on
120837	.969		.0	15	42		pump off
121025	.970		.1	15	42		pump on
121640	.967		10.1	15	43		pump off
121830	.966		7.2	15	43		pump on
122300	.963		.0	15	43		pump off
122420	.964		.5	15	43		pump on
123050	.960		2.7	15	43		pump off
123225	.959		8.8	15	43		pump on
124210	.956		4.0	15	43		pump off
132346	.950		.9	15	43		pump on
132620	.929		.0	15	43		pump off
140900	.927		2.1	15	43		pump on
142248	.922		.0	14	42		pump off
143850	.929		2.7	15	42		pump on
145800	.923		.0	14	43		pump off
141050	.922		.0	14	43		pump on

size	#	charged/by	Flight/Date	declared/by	Comments
10 1	1 } 2 }	2/11 KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	Water Tree
10 1	3 } 4 }	2/11 KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	Water Tree
10 1	7 } 8 }	2/11 KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	
10 1	10 } 69 }	2/11 /KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	blank
10 1	21 } 23 }	2/11 KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	
10 1	33 } 40 }	2/11 KNS	B413 3/11	3/11 KNS	

filter No	Loc N	T _{on}	T _{off}	Run	Acc Vol	
12 -	L	132400	133230	TRAPPING	4424	
3,4 -	V	132400	13290	TRAPPING	3504	
10,69 -	V	133118	13550		1176	
7,8 -	L	143635	144517		7444	Blank
21,23 -	V	143835	144517		349	
33,40 -	V	145300	145800		280	

CVI log

11/3/08 10:28:01 AM lyman zero
11/3/08 10:28:16 AM preflight ok
11/3/08 10:30:00 AM Manchester cloud physics rack plumbed for 1lpm with no instrumentation, use to shorte dead time.
11/3/08 11:09:56 AM hygro to sample
11/3/08 11:10:22 AM hygro to sample
11/3/08 11:11:49 AM tip heater at sp of 20C.
11/3/08 11:13:06 AM tip heater at sp of 20C.
11/3/08 11:13:20 AM PCASP flow adjusted down slightly
11/3/08 11:13:53 AM cf on ready for 3000ft set up.
11/3/08 11:14:22 AM cf on ready for 3000ft set up.
11/3/08 11:16:12 AM AMS not ready
11/3/08 11:16:53 AM AMS on
11/3/08 11:20:00 AM manchester cloud physics switching
11/3/08 11:22:47 AM
11/3/08 11:27:27 AM AMS not on cvi
11/3/08 11:27:44 AM AMS not on cvi valves in wrong position
11/3/08 11:28:01 AM AMS not on cvi valves in wrong position
11/3/08 11:28:41 AM AMS on CVI
11/3/08 11:29:14 AM AMS on CVI 0.72
11/3/08 11:31:14 AM zero not working, just go with standard settings
11/3/08 11:32:39 AM cf cntl to 2.0
11/3/08 11:32:57 AM cf at 2.84 samp at 2.25
11/3/08 11:33:08 AM cloud
11/3/08 11:36:28 AM saw cloud ok.
11/3/08 11:37:23 AM cf to cntl 1 at 50ft just to see what base line is.
11/3/08 11:37:30 AM cf to cntl 1 at 50ft just to see what base line is.
11/3/08 11:38:05 AM cf at 2.68 lpm samp at 2.32lpm still got flat line.
11/3/08 11:39:03 AM in cloud
11/3/08 11:41:34 AM reasonable zero with cf cntle of 1.0
11/3/08 11:44:18 AM in cloud
11/3/08 11:46:25 AM concentrations seem to low. Cf still to high, is sample flow really that high at 2.32?
11/3/08 11:46:43 AM play with zero at 50ft
11/3/08 11:47:01 AM cf to 0.5
11/3/08 11:47:54 AM cf to 0.5
11/3/08 11:48:07 AM AMS flow to 6.2
11/3/08 11:48:40 AM AMS flow to 0.0
11/3/08 11:50:15 AM cf cntl to 2.5
11/3/08 11:51:25 AM cloud, cf cntl =2 no ams dial flow.
11/3/08 11:52:10 AM Still concentrations in cloud low.
11/3/08 11:53:41 AM CF cntl to 1.5
11/3/08 11:53:50 AM CF cntl to 1.5
11/3/08 11:55:10 AM cf off, aerosol mode at 5000ft
11/3/08 11:58:26 AM PCASP flow adjusted
11/3/08 11:59:15 AM cf mode cntle=1.5
11/3/08 12:00:59 PM cf mode cntle=1.5 cf =1.76lpm samp at 1.49.
11/3/08 12:02:23 PM cloud
11/3/08 12:05:03 PM
11/3/08 12:05:47 PM cf closed aerosol mode
11/3/08 12:08:19 PM cf on ready for cloud crossing
11/3/08 12:09:04 PM passing through some cumulas cloud
11/3/08 12:10:16 PM out of cloud
11/3/08 12:11:51 PM aerosiol mode above cloud
11/3/08 12:16:47 PM cloud
11/3/08 12:18:53 PM aerosol mode
11/3/08 12:28:33 PM PCASP adjusted down
11/3/08 12:31:04 PM cloud
11/3/08 12:32:55 PM aerosol mode
11/3/08 12:34:15 PM cas liquid water content 0,3 to 0.5. CVI hygro well low!!
11/3/08 12:41:05 PM set up cf cntl at 1.3 with just ams
11/3/08 12:42:31 PM cf to 1, looking for some aerosol
11/3/08 12:42:43 PM cf to 1, looking for some aerosol
11/3/08 12:42:48 PM cf to 1, looking for some aerosol
11/3/08 12:43:22 PM adjusting ams dial for base line.
11/3/08 12:43:37 PM
11/3/08 12:44:53 PM In cloud run, no cloud at start

11/3/08 12:45:03 PM
11/3/08 12:45:54 PM
11/3/08 12:47:35 PM
11/3/08 12:49:49 PM ams flow down to 0.3
11/3/08 12:50:43 PM in cloud
11/3/08 12:51:15 PM cloud very thin
11/3/08 12:54:53 PM cas values agree with cvi NON EF mode.
11/3/08 12:56:30 PM cas values agree with cvi NON EF mode.
11/3/08 1:17:27 PM patchy cloud
11/3/08 1:20:54 PM no cloud
11/3/08 1:24:09 PM cf off aerosol mode.
11/3/08 1:26:48 PM aerosol layer just above cloud tops
11/3/08 1:56:37 PM cf mode for cloud transition to low level
11/3/08 1:58:29 PM aerosol mode
11/3/08 2:21:35 PM cf on ready fror in cloud run
11/3/08 2:21:44 PM cf on ready fror in cloud run
11/3/08 2:24:29 PM cloud
11/3/08 2:36:17 PM above cloud, aerosol mode
11/3/08 2:45:52 PM cf on for cloud transition
11/3/08 2:46:06 PM cf on for cloud transition Bit late Ooops
11/3/08 2:47:58 PM aerosol mode
11/3/08 2:58:26 PM
11/3/08 2:58:38 PM cf on with ams
11/3/08 2:59:54 PM in cloud
11/3/08 3:11:21 PM last run used 0.72, forgot to use 0.3, but data looked similar??
11/3/08 3:11:35 PM aerosol mode for sondes.
11/3/08 3:11:57 PM aerosol mode for sondes.
11/3/08 4:11:08 PM hygro switched to ref flow

ARIES flight log

Flight: B413 page 1 of 2

Date: 03/Nov/2008 Operator(s): S. Rogers Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc/Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0900	On the ground						Power on OK.
093340	"		CH	C	71	32	Cold Start Min. script
110335	Take off		-	C	71	31	P1 ↑ at take off.
1110	6000ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 3sec.
111214	↓						↳ descend drag 2
1115	3000ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 3sec. end 11.28
1128	↑			C	71	31	
112910	5000ft		NZ	O	71	31	Nad Zen Long Run 3sec end
113150	↓ P4		N	C	71	31	Nad - Long Run 3min script (1)
113658	↑ P5			C	71	32	↳ 50ft → 5000ft
114207	↓ P6			C	71	31	5000ft → 50ft
114832	↑ P7			C	71	31	50ft → 6000ft
115450	↳ 6000ft			C	71	31	
115920	P8 ↓			C	71	31	6000ft → 50ft
120654	P9 ↑			C	71	31	50ft → 6000ft
121313	P10 ↓			C	71	31	6000ft → 50ft
122057	P11 ↑			C	71	31	50ft → 6000ft
122710	P12 ↓			C	71	31	6000ft → 50ft
12344	P13 ↑			C	71	31	50ft → 2500ft. 3500ft
123834	P5 3500ft			C	71	31	
124050	3500			C	71	31	End of script (1)
124411	2500ft			C	71	31	Nad - Long Run 3min
124802	↓ P14			C	71	31	descend to 2200ft In cloud
1302							Script aborted - locked up.
130317			CH	C	71	31	Cold Start Min. script
130949	3500ft		N	C	71	31	Nad - Long Run 3min script
132604	R9						
132655			Z	O	71	31	Zenit Long Run 3min Above cloud Ci above
1336	6000		-	C	71	31	
133800	4500ft?		N	C	71	31	Nad - Long Run 3min
1342	↑ 4500		Z	O	71	31	Zenit Long Run 3min

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	3/11/08	Flight	B413	log pages	4
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown		Campaign	VOCALS		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	Still attached					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	Yup					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	Roger					•
FERA on	at time					0854
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	19.0°C	Ch 17	19.0°C	Ch18	19.0°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					0608
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.6	Cold	288.9		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					0614
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.51	Cold	288.93	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	40.39	31.23	38.76	43.72	42.93	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Flight #	B413	Date	3/11/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
0930			Start up offered no problems – all ok. MARSS pod switched off to prevent overheating. Will try and remember to switch it on again at some point later						
1030			Yey me. Remembered to switch the MARSS pod on again.						
1039			Take off will be start of profile 1						
110335	P1↑	0	Profile 1 start climb to FL060						
			Below 4/8 Ci1						
110947	P1	FL060	End of profile 1						
110947	1	FL060	Start of run 1 Below 4/8 Ci1						
111214	P2↓	FL060	Start of profile 2 to FL030						
111517	P2↓	FL030	End of profile 2						
111517	2	FL030	Start or run below 4/8 Ci1						
112400	2	FL030	Start of run above 8/8 SC5 below 4/8 Ci1						
112654	2	FL030	End of run 2 above 8/8 SC5 below 4/8 Ci1						
112654	P3↑	FL030	Start of profile ascent to FL050 above 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci1						
112846	P3↑	FL050	End of profile ascent at FL050 above 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci1						
112846	4	FL050	Start or run above 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci1						
113052	4	FL050	End of run above 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci1						
113052	P4↓	FL050	Start of profile descent to 50ft above 8/8 Sc5 below 4/8 Ci1						
113315	P4↓		Entering Sc5 circa FL027						
113515	P4↓		Below Sc5 circa FL018						
113654	P4↓	50ft	End of profile descent						
113654	P5↑	50ft	Start of profile ascent to FL050 below 8/8 Sc5						
113915	P5↑		Into Sc5 circa FL021						
114001	P5↑		Above 8/8 Sc5 below 3/8 Ci1 circa FL028						
114205	P5↑	FL050	End of profile						
114205	P6↓	FL050	Start of profile descent to 50ft above 8/8 Sc5 below 3/8 Ci1						
114405	P6↓	FL030	Entering Sc5						
114530	P6↓	FL019	Below Sc5						
114827	P6↓	50ft	End of profile descent below 8/8 Sc5						
114827	P7↑	50ft	Start of profile climb to FL060						
115055	P7↑	FL020	Entering 8/8 Sc5						
115130	P7↑	FL028	Above 8/8 Sc5 below 2/8 Ci1						
115451	P7↑	FL060	End of profile ascent						
115915	P8↓	FL060	Start of profile descent to 50ft from point 1 above 8/8 Sc5 below 2/8 Ci1						
120240	P8↓	FL029	Entering 8/8 Sc5						
120341	P8↓	FL020	Below 8/8 Sc5						
120655	P8↓	50ft	End of profile descent						
120655	P9↑	50ft	Start of profile climb to FL060 below 8/8 Sc5						
			Missed cloud transit, sorry but talk of thin pollution layer around FL030 which MARSS may be seeing traces of??						
121313	P9↑	FL060	End of profile ascent						

<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>	Sys
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121313	P10 ↓	FL060	Start of profile descent to 50ft above 8/8 Sc5 below 1/8 Ci1	
			Entered SC5 around F1027	
122057	P10 ↓	50ft	End of profile descent at 50ft	
122057	P11 ↑	50ft	Start of profile ascent to below 8/8 Sc5	
123240	P11 ↑	FL060	End of profile ascent above 8/8 Sc5 below 1/8 Ci1	
123240	P12 ↓	FL060	Start of profile to 50ft	
	P12 ↓		Cloud now 6/8 Sc5 with 1/8 Ci1 above	
123453	P12 ↓	50ft	End of profile descent	
123453	P13 ↑	50ft	Start of profile climb to FL033	
123837	P13 ↑	FL033	Cloud now 2/8 Sc5	
123837	P13 ↑	FL033	End of profile climb	
123837	5	FL033	Start of run	
124114	5	FL033	Point 2 and end of run	
124411	6	FL025	Start of run in point 2 due in cloud at FL025	
			Currently not in Sc5 and below 2/8 Ci1	
	6	FL025	End of run. Descending to FL022 as we missed the cloud layer	
124834	P14 ↓	FL025	End of profile descent	
124834	7	FL022	Start of run	
125000	7	FL022	Into cloud	
125144	7	FL022	End of run	
125144	P15 ↑	FL022	Start of profile climb	
125206	P15 ↑	FL025	End of profile climb	
125206	8	FL025	Start of run still attempting to be in cloud hence the height changes. Cloud thickens to the NW (which is the direction of this run)	
132200	8	FL025	End of run	
132200	P16 ↑	FL025	Start of profile climb	
132314	P16 ↑	FL035	End of profile climb	
132601	9	FL035	Start of run above 8/8 Sc5 in pollution layer and below 3/8 Ci1	
133606	9	FL035	End of run	
133606	P17 ↑	FL035	Start of profile ascent to FL045 above 8/8 Sc5 and below 3/8 Ci1	
133726	P17 ↑	FL043	End of profile ascent	
133726	10	FL043	Start of run followed by mini profile to FL045	
133946	11	FL045	Start of run	
134120	P18 ↑	FL045	Start of profile climb	
134120	12	FL054	Start of run	
134440	P19 ↑	FL054	Start of profile climb	
134508	13	FL058	Start of run	
134645	P20 ↓	FL058	Start of profile descent	
134938	14	FL033	Start of run	
134959	P21 ↓	FL033	Start of profile descent	
135027	15	FL032	Start of run	
			From 133726 to 135547 all completed above Sc5 and below 3/8 Ci1	
135547	P22 ↓	FL032	Start of profile descent to FL018 at point 3	
1357	P22 ↓		Entered Sc5 layer FL025 approx	

Flight #	B413	Date	3/11/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	4	of	4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
135819	P22↓	FL014	End of profile descent to below Sc5 cloud						
135946	16	FL014	Start of below cloud run						
1406	16	FL014	Out from under sc5 layer						
140906	P23↓	FL014	Start of profile descent to FL001						
			2/8 SC5 3/8 Ci1 and we're below both						
141122	17	FL001	Start of run Sc5 now 6/8!						
1415	17	FL001	Now below 7.5/8 Sc5						
1419	17	FL001	Noted embedded 1/8 Cu1 in 7/8 Sc5 layer						
142120	P24↑	FL001	Start of profile climb to FL032						
142422	18	FL032	Start of in cloud run – looks like new layer below at about FL020 which may be Cu base height. Not sure what base of Sc5 is at, though appears pretty thin at this level						
143423	P25↑	FL032	Start of profile climb for above cloud run						
143507	19	FL040	Start of above cloud run 8/8 sc5 below 2/8 Ci1 above						
1441	19		Don't appear to be any Cu tops above the Sc5 layer so perhaps it's been an Sc4 layer all the time. Though I can't see 8/8 Sc5 forming out of 1/8 Cu – I'll leave it as embedded.						
1442	19	FL04?	Cloud layer thickening so run will have gentle climb element.						
144509	P26↓	FL042	Start of profile descent to 50 ft and immediately into cloud layer						
144710	P26↓	FL019	Below cloud – can't see any Cu bases now so that would explain the lack of Cu tops in the 8/8 Sc5						
145036	P27↑	50ft	Profile ascent to FL025 below 8/8 Sc5 at point 4						
145239	20	FL025	Start of below cloud run 8/8 Sc5						
145755	P28↑	FL025	Start of profile to FL040 in cloud						
145944	21	FL040	Start of run						
1204	21	FL038	Dropping 200 ft to remain in cloud						
1208	21	FL038	Only just in cloud layer as again breaking through tops						
150950	P29↑	FL038	Start of profile climb to FL230						
152822	22	FL230	Start or run above 7/8 Sc5 below 3/8 Ci1						
1539	22	FL230	SC5 now 4/8 Ci 3/8						
153946	P30↓	FL230	Start of profile descent into Arica so will be difficult to note end of science						
			Sc5 below between 4/8 and 7/8 during return run						
1548	P30↓		Over 8/8 Sc5 and under very thin Ci1 layer of about 6/8						
1555	P30↓		Clear of Sc5 layer now so nil below – Ci1 remains at 6/8 and thin above.						
1600547	P30	0	End of profile. End of science.						

B413_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:44:19.80 --- - - - -
09:44:19.80 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:44:19.80 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:44:19.80 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. 413
09:44:19.81 --- - - - -
09:44:31.49 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
09:44:34.25 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:44:34.99 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:44:35.76 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:44:39.85 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:44:44.81 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:44:49.14 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:44:50.11 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:44:51.88 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:44:52.07 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:44:54.75 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:44:57.57 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:44:57.61 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:44:59.57 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:45:02.71 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:45:02.71 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:45:04.95 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:45:11.62 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:45:11.66 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
09:45:15.92 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:15.92 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:15.93 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:51.48 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:45:56.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:45:56.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:45:57.70 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:45:59.00 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:59.14 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:01.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:04.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:04.81 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:07.13 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:07.71 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:10.70 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:46:18.71 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:46:26.21 SWS - - - - Idling
09:46:26.23 USH - - - - Idling
09:46:26.34 LSH - - - - Idling
09:46:32.85 --- - - - - *** 11 deg
09:54:25.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:54:25.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:54:25.20 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:54:32.67 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:54:39.26 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:54:41.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:54:41.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:54:44.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:19:37.92 --- - - - - *** 9 deg
10:19:46.78 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:19:46.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:19:46.82 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:19:47.31 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:19:47.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:19:48.94 SWS - - - - Idling
10:19:49.35 USH - - - - Idling
10:19:52.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:19:52.53 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:19:53.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:23:34.32 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:23:37.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:23:39.23 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

10:23:40.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:21.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:22.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:35.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:35.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:35.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:37.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:37.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:39.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:39.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:41.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:41.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:42.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:42.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:42.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:43.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:43.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:51.24	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:25:51.25	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:25:53.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:53.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:53.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:54.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:55.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:55.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:55.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:25:56.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:25:57.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:00.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:01.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:01.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:01.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:02.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:02.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:07.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:14.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:14.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:14.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:40.66	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:26:40.66	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:26:42.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:43.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:44.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:45.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:47.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:48.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:51.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:57.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:10.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:34:48.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:50:49.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:49.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:49.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:50.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:50.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:50.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:01:27.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
11:01:28.95	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:02:30.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:05.27	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:05:06.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:09:40.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:40.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:40.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:41.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:41.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:47.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:38.55	LSH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 100ms to 1000ms.

11:15:45.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:45.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:46.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:15:47.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:47.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:47.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:53.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:41.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:22:00.74	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
11:22:02.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:05.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:07.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:10.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:13.63	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
11:22:13.64	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 200ms.
11:22:16.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:19.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:21.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:22:24.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:44.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
11:22:54.72	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:22:57.27	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:23:07.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** over flying low cloud
11:23:17.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:26:27.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:27.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:27.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:41.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:41.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:41.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:42.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:43.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:44.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:47.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:47.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:47.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:48.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:48.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:50.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:52.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:52.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:52.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:26:53.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:53.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:55.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:17.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:17.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:17.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:21.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:21.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:21.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:27:21.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:22.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:23.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:19.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:30:52.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
11:33:14.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** enteron cloud
11:34:06.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
11:36:19.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:37:02.15	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:37:03.87	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:39:13.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through cloud
11:41:36.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** above stratocumulus sheet
11:44:55.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:45:43.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:43.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:43.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:48.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:48.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:45:48.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:49.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:50.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:51.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:52.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:52.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:52.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:53.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:54.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:55.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:56.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:56.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:56.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:45:56.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:57.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:58.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:46:07.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:07.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:07.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:34.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:54:39.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:56:52.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:52.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:56:52.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:10.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:10.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:10.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:11.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:11.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:13.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:13.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:13.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:57:14.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:14.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:16.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:57:22.90	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:57:24.62	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:57:25.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:25.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:57:25.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:22.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
12:03:06.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:03:25.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 2900 ft
12:06:56.51	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:06:58.25	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:07:47.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:10:12.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
12:11:56.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:17:18.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:18.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:18.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:22.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:22.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:22.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:23.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:24.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:25.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:25.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:25.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:25.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:26.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:26.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:28.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:28.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:28.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:28.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:29.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:30.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:17:31.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:17:36.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:36.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:36.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:26.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:28:46.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:46.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:46.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:52.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:52.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:53.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:53.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:55.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:55.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:55.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:55.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:56.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:56.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:57.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:58.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:58.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:58.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:59.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:59.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:29:00.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:29:07.73	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:29:09.45	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:29:11.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:11.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:11.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:21.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:31:34.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** just gone through cloud
12:31:42.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** still in cloud
12:31:54.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
12:31:58.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:32:22.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** this is profile 11 from 6000 ft to 50 ft
12:32:42.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction profile 12
12:34:45.84	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:34:47.53	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:35:13.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 13 climbing to 5000 ft from 50 ft
12:36:54.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:39:03.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3300 ft
12:40:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:41:17.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending to 2000 ft
12:44:03.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2500 ft - in cloud run
12:44:23.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:23.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:23.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:34.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:34.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:34.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:35.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:35.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:37.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:37.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:37.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:37.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:38.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:38.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:40.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:41.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:41.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:41.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:44:42.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:42.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:44.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:44:50.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:44:50.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

12:44:50.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:14.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** descent to 2200 ft
12:48:36.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** to get into cloud layer now run 7
12:51:16.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** in very thin cloud
12:51:34.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:52:19.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8 at 2400 ft
12:52:45.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** now near cloud top in run 7 were near
cloud base						
12:52:52.20	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:52:52.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:52:53.96	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:52:54.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:53:10.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:10.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:10.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:11.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:11.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:13.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:09.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:09.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:09.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:12.16	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:57:13.83	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:57:26.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:26.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:27.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:27.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:29.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:29.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:29.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:29.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:30.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:30.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:31.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:31.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:57:32.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:32.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:32.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:37.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:37.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:37.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:57:56.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:05:13.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:06:09.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:08:08.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:08.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:08.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:14.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:14.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:14.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:15.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:15.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:16.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:17.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:17.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:17.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:18.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:18.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:20.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:21.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:21.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:21.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:22.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:22.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:24.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:08:32.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:32.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:32.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

13:09:11.53	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:09:13.27	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:12:47.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:19:28.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:19:33.43	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:19:34.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:19:35.17	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:19:46.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:46.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:46.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:51.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:51.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:51.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:52.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:52.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:54.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:54.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:54.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:54.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:55.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:55.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:57.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:57.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:57.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:57.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:19:58.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:59.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:00.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:02.05	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:20:02.07	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
13:20:04.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:04.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:04.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:05.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:06.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:07.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:09.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:09.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:09.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:09.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:10.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:11.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:11.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:20:11.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:12.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:12.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:20:17.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:17.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:20:17.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:21:20.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:22:00.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:22:54.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud
13:23:02.23	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:23:03.95	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:23:27.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:27.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:27.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:31.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:31.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:31.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:32.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:32.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:33.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:33.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:34.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:34.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:35.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:35.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:23:35.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:36.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:36.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:37.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:01.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:01.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:01.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:54.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:26:13.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 9
13:26:33.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3500 ft in aerosol layer above cloud top
13:27:19.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:19.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:19.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:28.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:28.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:28.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:29.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:29.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:30.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:31.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:31.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:31.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:32.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:34.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:35.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:35.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:35.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:35.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:36.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:37.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:46.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:46.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:46.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:05.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** note there are small quantities of dust
inside the SHIMS	ab BBR domes					
13:32:17.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
13:33:55.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 deg11
13:34:01.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
13:36:08.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:36:51.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:51.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:51.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:58.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:58.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:58.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:59.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:59.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:00.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:00.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:00.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:00.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:01.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:01.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:03.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:04.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:04.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:04.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:04.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:05.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:06.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:37:17.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:17.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:17.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:26.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run at 4500 ft
13:39:54.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** broken by several profile climbs and
restarted runs						
13:40:03.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4700 ft
13:42:47.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg

13:43:05.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 5000 and something feet
13:46:41.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:47:09.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 20
13:48:13.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:13.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:14.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:22.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:22.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:22.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:23.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:23.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:25.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:25.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:25.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:25.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:26.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:27.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:28.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:29.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:29.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:29.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:30.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:30.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:31.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:48:43.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:43.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:43.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:34.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3500 ft
13:50:06.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run descebding
13:50:38.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 15 at 3300 ft
13:51:40.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:55:53.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:56:01.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning at point 3
13:56:18.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** and descending to below cloud
13:56:41.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:56:43.27	SWS	-5.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:57:17.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
13:57:52.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base
13:58:57.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 1800 ft
13:59:41.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** dipping down to 1500 ft
14:00:22.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:01:55.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:02:04.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:04.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:04.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:10.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:10.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:10.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:11.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:11.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:13.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:13.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:13.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:13.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:14.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:14.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:16.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:17.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:17.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:17.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:18.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:18.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:20.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:24.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:24.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:24.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:24.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:25.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:25.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:02:26.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:26.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:26.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:27.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:27.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:02:27.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:27.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:27.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:20.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:07:48.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** ebd of run
14:09:00.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run and start of profile
14:09:13.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** descent to 100 ft
14:09:41.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** that was end of run 16
14:11:30.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 17 at 100 ft
14:14:40.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:16:21.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:21.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:21.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:27.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:27.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:27.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:28.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:28.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:30.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:30.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:30.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:30.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:31.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:31.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:33.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:34.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:34.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:34.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:35.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:37.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:43.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:43.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:43.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:21.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile climb into cloud
14:21:34.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:24:21.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
14:24:27.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
14:24:34.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:34.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:34.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:39.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:39.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:39.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:40.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:41.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:42.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:43.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:43.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:43.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:44.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:44.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:46.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:46.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:46.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:46.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:47.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:48.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:49.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:52.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:52.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:52.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:26:22.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:31:18.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:33:30.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:30.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:31.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:31.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:36.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:36.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:36.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:37.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:37.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:39.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:39.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:39.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:40.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:40.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:41.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:42.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:47.29	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:33:47.30	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:33:49.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:49.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:49.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:51.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:51.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:51.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:51.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:52.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:52.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:52.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:55.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:55.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:55.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:56.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:56.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:33:58.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:34:04.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:04.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:04.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:17.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:34:26.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:34:34.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing above cloud
14:34:49.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** p 24
14:35:02.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 3800 ft cloud top
14:35:08.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 4000 ft
14:35:14.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:14.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:14.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:20.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:20.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:20.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:20.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:21.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:22.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:24.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:24.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:24.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:24.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:25.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:26.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:31.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:31.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:31.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:36.05	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:35:37.83	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:37:35.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:40:20.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:41:55.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:55.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:41:55.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:03.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:03.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:03.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:03.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:04.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:05.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:06.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:06.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:06.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:07.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:07.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:09.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:10.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:10.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:10.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:12.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:12.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:13.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:17.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:17.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:17.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:43:04.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:45:13.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:45:19.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
14:49:08.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** down to 50 ft, at 50 ft will change to zwnith view
14:50:33.10	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:50:34.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:51:43.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:43.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:43.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:50.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:50.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:50.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:51.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:51.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:53.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:54.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:54.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:54.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:55.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:55.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:57.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:58.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:58.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:58.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:51:59.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:00.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:08.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:08.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:08.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:20.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:52:47.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2500 ft
14:53:00.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:00.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:00.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:05.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:05.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:05.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:06.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:06.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:08.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:09.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:09.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:09.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:10.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:10.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:53:12.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:13.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:13.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:14.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:14.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:16.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:53:21.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:21.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:21.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:15.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:57:58.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:58:04.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:58:11.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
14:58:35.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:58:40.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:58:45.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:45.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:45.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:51.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:51.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:51.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:52.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:52.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:54.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:54.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:54.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:54.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:55.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:56.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:56.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:56.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:58:57.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:58.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:58:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:59:08.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:08.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:08.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:01.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** run in cloud 4000 ft
15:00:08.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:01:02.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:02.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:02.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:08.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:08.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:09.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:09.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:10.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:11.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:11.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:11.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:12.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:12.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:14.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:15.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:15.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:15.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:01:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:16.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:18.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:24.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:24.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:24.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:08.77	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:02:10.54	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:04:21.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:04:36.94	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:04:38.73	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

15:06:20.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:06:27.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:27.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:27.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:33.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:33.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:33.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:33.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:34.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:35.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:37.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:37.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:37.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:38.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:39.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:40.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:40.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:40.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:41.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:42.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:43.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:50.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:50.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:50.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:54.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:10:14.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to FL 230
15:12:30.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:30.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:30.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:36.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:36.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:36.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:36.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:37.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:38.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:39.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:39.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:39.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:40.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:40.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:41.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:42.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:42.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:42.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:43.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:43.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:45.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:51.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:12:53.69	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:13:20.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:13:20.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:13:20.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:17:48.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:17:48.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:17:48.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:17:48.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:17:59.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:59.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:17:59.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:00.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:00.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:02.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:03.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:03.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:03.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:04.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:04.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:05.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:18:07.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:07.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:07.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:18:08.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:08.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:09.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:22.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:18:22.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:18:22.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:10.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:26:10.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:26:12.58	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:26:18.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:18.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:18.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:18.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:18.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:18.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:24.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:24.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:24.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:25.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:25.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:27.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:28.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:28.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:28.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:29.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:29.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:31.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:33.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:33.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:33.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:26:34.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:34.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:36.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:26:45.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:45.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:45.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:26:51.40	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:26:53.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:27:21.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:29:33.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 230 started\after first sonde
15:31:26.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:26.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:26.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:35.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:35.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:36.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:36.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:37.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:43.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:43.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:43.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:44.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:44.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:45.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:46.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:46.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:46.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:47.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:47.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:49.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:54.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:54.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:54.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:46.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
15:34:35.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:34:35.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:35.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:35.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:37.71	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:34:39.46	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:34:46.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:46.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:46.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:47.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:48.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:49.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:50.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:50.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:50.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:51.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:51.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:53.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:56.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:56.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:57.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:16.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:36:14.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:14.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:14.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:18.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:18.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:19.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:19.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:20.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:21.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:23.31	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:36:25.08	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:36:29.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:29.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:29.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:42.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:39:47.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:40:10.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 30 descending into Arica
15:41:00.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:00.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:00.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:08.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:41:10.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:41:18.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:18.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:18.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:19.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:19.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:21.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:22.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:22.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:22.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:24.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:25.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:26.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:26.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:26.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:27.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:27.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:29.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:32.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:32.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:42.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** high level clear skies above flaring on
15:43:47.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:48.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:48.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:43:52.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:52.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:52.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:53.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:53.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:55.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:56.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:56.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:57.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:57.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:58.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:43:59.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:44:00.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:00.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:00.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:01.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:44:01.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:44:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:44:08.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:44:09.95	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:44:11.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:11.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:15.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:49:25.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud sheet thickening below
15:50:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:13.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:13.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:19.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:19.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:20.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:21.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:21.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:22.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:23.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:23.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:23.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:24.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:24.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:26.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:27.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:27.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:27.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:28.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:28.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:29.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:50:36.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:36.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:36.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:38.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:38.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:38.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:42.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:08:43.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:08:48.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:48.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:48.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:49.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:50.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:51.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:52.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:52.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:52.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:53.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:53.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:55.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:55.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:55.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:55.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:08:56.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:56.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:08:58.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:01.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:01.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:01.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:02.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:09:08.51	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
16:09:08.52	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
16:09:13.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:13.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:13.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:17.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:17.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:17.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:18.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:18.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:20.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:22.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:22.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:22.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:22.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:23.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:24.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:25.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:25.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:25.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:26.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:26.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:28.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:31.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:31.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:31.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:10:27.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
16:10:29.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:10:29.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:10:29.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:10:29.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

Flight:

B413

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B413

Date: 03/11/08

Instruments

RFC	condensation running on inside of window
Filters	water in pipes lead to wetting of papers
Dropsondes	4 dropped, 1 did not lock to GPS
CVI -	trouble zeroing at start of flight.
Neph –PSAP – wetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem -	Low ozone values causing either paranoia or evidence of instrument fault.
Cloud physics -	PCASP – leak near inlet jet?
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	ok
CCN -	single channel only, u/s connector found post-flight
VACC -	ok
2DS -	ok, one crash in cloud, reset ok
CAPS -	ok,
SMPS -	ok at low level
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

MPDS
Run for flight

Satcom-H Calls
nil

Issues

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 3/11/08

Flight No: B413

Pre-Flighter: KFT.

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☐	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	DA	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	<i>Mubbish on CCN/rad2</i>
4	DA	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	DA	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
10	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	X	FWWS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	<i>adjusted</i>
21	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	✓	Satcom C	Checked	
23	X	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	X	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	DT	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	DT	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	X	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	<i>stuff in clear BBR</i>
36	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	<i>residue on lens</i>
38	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	✓	All other covers	Removed	
40	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more	
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B413:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
CCN	CCN operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
PAN log	PAN does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110552_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110656_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_120656_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_130656_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_140656_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_150656_1hz.av
faam-video-dfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_160656_1hz.av

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110542_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_120656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_130656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_140656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_150656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_160656_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110545_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110656_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_120656_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_130656_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_140656_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_150656_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_160656_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110548_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_110656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_120656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_130656_1hz.av
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_140656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_150656_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20081103_r0_b413_160656_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.